

Synthesis of Some New Δ^4 -Thiazolines and Their Mercurated Derivatives and Their Possible Use as Pesticides

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Fifteen symmetrical diarylthioureas have been condensed with various saturated as well as α - β -unsaturated ketones in presence of bromine or iodine as the condensing agent leading to the formation of some new 2-arylamino-3-aryl-4-substituted- Δ^4 -thiazolines. Further they have been mercurated by mercuric acetate to give their mono-acetoxy mercuric derivatives. Both types of compounds have been assayed for their fungicidal activity against *Pyricularia oryzae* (Cav), the causative organism for the rice blast and bactericidal activity against the common pathogenic bacteria *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* and the results are quite promising.

THE versatile applications of thiazoles, thiazolines and thiazolidines and their derivatives have made this an area of extensive research by synthetic organic chemists. The recent applications of this class of compounds such as analgesic and anti-pyretic¹, anthelmintic², acaricidal³, pesticidal⁴ and particularly their use as effective fungicides⁵ have greatly enhanced their synthetic importance and biological testing.

In this laboratory, a number of such compounds and their mercurated derivatives have been synthesised and tested against the pathogenic bacteria and fungi. In view of the above observations, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise some more new thiazoline derivatives to test their fungicidal as well as bactericidal activity.

In the present communication, attempt has been made to synthesise some new Δ^4 -thiazolines by condensing various saturated as well as alpha-beta-unsaturated ketones with different symmetrical

diarylthioureas separately in presence of iodine or bromine as the condensing agent.

Fifteen different sym. diarylthioureas have been condensed with four saturated ketones namely *p*-methylacetophenone, *p*-ethylacetophenone, *m*-nitroacetophenone and cyclohexanone separately using bromine as the condensing agent and the products were 2-arylimino-3-aryl-4-substituted- Δ^4 -thiazolines, in case of the first three ketones and 2-arylimino-3-aryl-4,5-tetramethylene- Δ^4 -thiazolines in case of the last one. The structures were confirmed by the chemical methods adopted earlier^{6,7} and characteristic ir data.

Three α - β -unsaturated ketones namely *o*-chloro-benzylidene acetone, anisylidene acetone and mesityl oxide were condensed separately with different sym. diarylthioureas in presence of bromine or iodine as the condensing agent.

But this possibility is discarded as the resultant product(III) failed to respond to the iodoform test showing that $\text{CH}_3-\text{CO}-$ group is absent in the molecule.

In presence of bromine, there is every possibility that the reaction might have proceeded through a dibromide intermediate. Bromine may add up initially to the unsaturated ketone to give the dibromide which may condense either of the two ways giving different products (IV and V) as shown below :

This possibility is ruled out as the final products (IV and V) contain a substituent at C_6 -position and the product failed to give the iodoform test.

The absence of peaks for carbonyl stretching and $\text{C}-\text{Br}$ stretching frequencies in the ir spectrum of the compound discards the possibilities of the structures III, IV and V. The possibility of reduction of unsaturated ketone by HI or HBr prior to their condensation is ruled out by the fact that in such case it would have given a C_6 -substituted compound which is never the case.

The above Δ^4 -thiazoline(II) has been mercurated with one equivalent of mercuric acetate in acetic acid medium at room temperature, when mono-acetoxymymeric compound is formed. It has been assumed that the acetoxymymeric group enters the N_5 -phenyl nucleus of the thiazoline moiety^{11,12} and the *para* position is preferred over the *ortho* position, if the former one is free¹³.

The position of acetoxymymeric group in the *para* position of N_5 -phenyl ring of the thiazoline nucleus is further confirmed from the following chemical evidence.

When the monoacetoxymymeric derivative(VI) of 2-phenylimino-3-phenyl-4- $[\beta$ -(*o*-chlorophenyl)ethyl]- Δ^4 -thiazoline(II) was treated with potassium perbromide solution, a mono bromo derivative(VII) was resulted, in which acetoxymymeric group is replaced by bromine. When compound (VII) was hydrolysed by dilute acid the compound (VIII) was formed which is identical with the hydrolysis product of 2-(*p*-bromophenyl) imino-3-(*p*-bromophenyl)-4- $[\beta$ -(*o*-chlorophenyl)ethyl]- Δ^4 -thiazoline(IX) synthesised independently from *o*-chlorobenzylidene acetone and sym. di(*p*-bromophenyl) thiourea.

(Table 1 Contd.)

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
$R' = (CH_2)_4$													
46.	C_6H_5-	180	10.05	10.42	6.0	+	+	240	35.38	35.46	3.5	+	+
47.	$o-Cl.C_6H_4-$	147	8.17	8.51	3.5	+	+	245	31.35	31.65	1.8	+	+
48.	$m-Cl.C_6H_4-$	157	8.09	8.51	3.5	-	-	> 250	31.45	31.65	1.8	-	-
49.	$p-Cl.C_6H_4-$	201d	8.29	8.51	3.5	-	-	247d	31.45	31.65	1.9	-	+
50.	$o-CH_3.C_6H_4-$	162	9.27	9.55	6.0	+	+	242d	33.47	33.73	3.5	+	+
51.	$m-CH_3.C_6H_4-$	143	9.13	9.55	5.5	+	+	235	33.47	33.73	2.8	-	+
52.	$p-CH_3.C_6H_4-$	210	9.30	9.55	5.5	+	+	> 250	33.51	33.73	2.8	-	-
53.	$o-CH_3.O.C_6H_4-$	121	8.43	8.71	6.0	+	+	> 250	32.00	32.06	3.2	-	-
54.	$m-CH_3.O.C_6H_4-$	150	8.36	8.71	6.5	+	+	> 250	31.95	32.06	3.5	+	-
55.	$p-CH_3.O.C_6H_4-$	192	8.51	8.71	6.0	+	+	245	31.98	32.06	3.5	+	+
56.	$o-NO_2.C_6H_4-$	200d	7.65	8.06	4.5	+	-	235	30.31	30.55	2.8	+	-
57.	$m-NO_2.C_6H_4-$	215	7.82	8.06	4.0	+	+	237d	30.32	30.55	2.5	-	-
58.	$p-NO_2.C_6H_4-$	> 250	7.87	8.06	4.0	-	-	> 250	30.45	30.55	2.5	-	-
59.	$o-COOH.C_6H_4-$	189	7.81	8.10	4.5	+	+	246	30.48	30.69	2.4	+	-
60.	$p-COOH.C_6H_4-$	212	7.75	8.10	4.5	-	-	> 250	30.44	30.69	2.4	-	-
$R' = (CH_2)_3CH-CH_2-$													
61.	C_6H_5-	104	10.22	10.38	6.0	+	+	220	36.02	36.04	2.8	+	+
62.	$o-Cl.C_6H_4-$	101	8.35	8.48	3.2	+	+	222	32.04	32.06	1.2	-	-
63.	$m-Cl.C_6H_4-$	112	8.26	8.48	3.0	-	-	210	32.04	32.06	1.2	-	-
64.	$p-Cl.C_6H_4-$	125	8.33	8.48	3.0	-	-	215	32.01	32.06	1.5	-	-
65.	$o-CH_3.C_6H_4-$	120	9.45	9.53	5.5	+	+	220	34.2	34.31	2.1	+	+
66.	$m-CH_3.C_6H_4-$	145	9.43	9.53	6.1	+	+	230	34.25	34.31	3.0	+	-
67.	$p-CH_3.C_6H_4-$	130	9.48	9.53	6.0	+	+	225	34.22	34.31	2.8	-	-
68.	$o-CH_3.O.C_6H_4-$	120	8.51	8.69	6.0	+	+	245	32.55	32.53	2.8	-	+
69.	$m-CH_3.O.C_6H_4-$	90	8.58	8.69	6.5	+	+	230	32.29	32.53	2.8	+	+
70.	$p-CH_3.O.C_6H_4-$	141	8.59	8.69	6.0	-	-	207	32.22	32.53	3.2	+	+
71.	$o-NO_2.C_6H_4-$	160	7.89	8.04	4.5	-	-	> 250	31.00	31.02	1.9	-	-
72.	$m-NO_2.C_6H_4-$	110	7.80	8.04	4.5	-	-	235	31.01	31.02	1.9	-	-
73.	$p-NO_2.C_6H_4-$	180	7.90	8.04	4.0	-	-	> 250	30.99	31.02	1.8	-	-
74.	$o-COOH.C_6H_4-$	92	8.04	8.08	4.2	+	+	225	31.06	31.12	1.7	-	-
75.	$p-COOH.C_6H_4-$	122	8.04	8.08	4.0	+	+	215	31.09	31.12	1.8	-	-
$R' = p-CH_3.O.C_6H_4.OH_2-CH_2-$													
76.	C_6H_5-	110	7.98	8.29	5.5	+	+	190	30.87	31.10	2.8	+	+
77.	$o-Cl.C_6H_4-$	140	7.50	7.63	2.5	-	-	235	28.23	28.51	1.2	-	-
78.	$m-Cl.C_6H_4-$	170	7.45	7.63	2.5	-	-	225	28.34	28.51	1.2	-	-
79.	$p-Cl.C_6H_4-$	201	7.29	7.63	2.5	-	-	> 250	28.2	28.51	1.2	-	-
80.	$o-CH_3.C_6H_4-$	150	7.23	7.72	5.0	+	+	248	23.61	23.81	2.4	+	+
81.	$m-CH_3.C_6H_4-$	120	7.43	7.72	5.0	+	+	197	29.34	29.81	2.8	+	+
82.	$p-CH_3.C_6H_4-$	160	7.22	7.72	5.5	+	+	> 250	29.11	29.81	2.8	+	+
83.	$o-CH_3.O.C_6H_4-$	152	7.02	7.17	4.5	+	+	235	28.11	23.45	2.1	+	+
84.	$m-CH_3.O.C_6H_4-$	140	7.12	7.17	5.0	+	+	> 250	28.34	23.45	2.5	+	+
85.	$p-CH_3.O.C_6H_4-$	130	6.98	7.17	4.5	-	-	240	28.40	23.45	2.2	+	+
86.	$o-NO_2.C_6H_4-$	155	6.61	6.72	3.1	+	+	> 250	26.97	27.29	1.8	+	+
87.	$m-NO_2.C_6H_4-$	153	6.57	6.72	3.0	-	-	> 250	26.81	27.29	1.8	-	-
88.	$p-NO_2.C_6H_4-$	181	6.52	6.72	3.5	-	-	190	26.79	27.29	1.7	+	+
89.	$o-COOH.C_6H_4-$	162	6.43	6.75	3.5	+	+	> 250	27.34	27.76	1.4	+	-
90.	$p-COOH.C_6H_4-$	143	6.52	6.75	4.0	+	-	> 250	27.20	27.76	1.8	-	-
$R' = o-Cl.C_6H_4-CH_2-CH_2-$													
91.	C_6H_5-	149	7.9	8.10	2.5	+	+	215	31.29	31.38	1.21	-	-
92.	$o-Cl.C_6H_4-$	130	6.59	6.96	1.5	-	-	> 250	28.19	28.32	0.8	-	-
93.	$m-Cl.C_6H_4-$	125	6.82	6.96	1.5	-	-	> 250	28.22	28.32	0.9	-	-
94.	$p-Cl.C_6H_4-$	135	6.79	6.96	1.5	-	-	235	28.19	28.32	0.8	-	-
95.	$o-CH_3.C_6H_4-$	111	7.52	7.64	2.4	+	+	240	30.02	30.07	1.5	+	-
96.	$m-CH_3.C_6H_4-$	150	7.59	7.64	2.5	+	+	248	30.01	30.07	1.5	-	-
97.	$p-CH_3.C_6H_4-$	145	7.59	7.64	2.0	-	-	245	30.05	30.07	1.5	-	-
98.	$o-CH_3.O.C_6H_4-$	150	6.95	7.10	2.2	+	+	235	28.52	28.69	1.25	-	-
99.	$m-CH_3.O.C_6H_4-$	155	7.06	7.10	2.0	-	-	220	28.50	28.69	1.2	-	-
100.	$p-CH_3.O.C_6H_4-$	115	6.92	7.10	2.0	-	-	> 250	28.50	28.69	1.1	-	-
101.	$o-NO_2.C_6H_4-$	150	6.29	6.59	1.8	-	-	> 250	27.29	27.32	1.0	-	-
102.	$m-NO_2.C_6H_4-$	180	6.42	6.59	1.8	-	-	> 250	27.25	27.32	1.1	-	-
103.	$p-NO_2.C_6H_4-$	139	6.42	6.59	1.8	-	-	245	27.20	27.32	0.9	-	-
104.	$o-COOH.C_6H_4-$	145	6.49	6.61	2.0	+	-	225	27.23	27.40	1.1	-	-
105.	$p-COOH.C_6H_4-$	215	6.55	6.61	2.0	+	-	> 250	27.32	27.40	1.2	-	-

'd' denotes decomposition temperature.
All melting points are taken in open capillary tube and are uncorrected.

with hot water and then treated with liquor ammonia to liberate the free base. The product was then filtered and crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 149°. The ir spectrum of the compound was recorded in KBr pellets and showed the peaks at 3028 cm^{-1} (C-H stretching for thiazoline), 1630 ($-\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{str.}$) cm^{-1} characteristics of a thiazoline nucleus. The analytical as well as m.ps. of other thiazolines are listed in Table 1.

2. *Preparation of 2-phenylimino-3-(p-acetoxy-mercuric phenyl)-4-[\beta-(o-chlorophenyl)ethyl]- Δ^4 -thiazoline(VI)*: The above thiazoline (1.5 g) was dissolved in acetic acid (glacial) and the solution was added to a solution of mercuric acetate (1.2 g) in acetic acid (glacial). The mixture was well stirred and kept overnight to complete the reaction. The precipitate was filtered and washed with water, m.p. 215°. The analytical data and m.ps. of other monoacetoxymercuric derivatives are listed in Table 1.

Fungicidal test: Both mercurated and non-mercurated thiazolines were assayed for their fungicidal activity against *Pyricularia oryzae* (Cav.) as the test fungus by Montgomery and Moore¹⁴ method. The results have been tabulated in Table 1, on the basis of the dilution in ppm for 50% spore germination.

Bactericidal test: All these compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity by Rideal-Walker¹⁵ serial drop dilution method against the common gram positive bacteria *S. aureus* and gram negative bacteria *E. coli*. The results on the basis of activity at 100 ppm have been given in Table 1.

Discussion

The result of fungicidal and bactericidal assessment reveals the following facts:

1. Both mercurated and non-mercurated thiazolines have got promising antifungal and antibacterial activity. The parent thiazolines are active at the concentration of 50-100 ppm against the fungus and 100-125 ppm against the bacteria.

2. A definite pattern exists between the structure and the activity.

(a) The substituents of C_2 -position and N_3 -position of the thiazoline nucleus contribute towards the activity with the following order:

(b) The substituents at C_4 -position of the nucleus contribute towards the activity as follows.

(c) Mercurated compounds are about two times more active than the parent thiazolines.

(d) Pesticidal activity does not depend upon saturation or unsaturation of the ketone. It definitely depends upon the presence or absence of chlorine in the molecule.

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